

Vegetable Proteins. Part II. Typhoidin—the Alcohol-Soluble Protein of *Pennisetum Typhoideum*.

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Cumbu (*Pennisetum typhoideum* ; Tamil name, Cumbu; Telugu, Sajjalu; Hindustani, Bajra), a staple food of a considerable proportion of the Indian cultivating classes, occupies the fourth place among the grain crops of India and is cultivated over an area of 16 million acres (*Dept. Com. Int. & St., India, 1928, 25*). It is purely a rain-fed crop and is largely grown along with *Cajanus Indicus* or pigeon pea. It is highly resistant to drought and in nutritive value compares favourably with other Indian cereals.

As the cereal enters into the diet of large classes of people, a biochemical examination of it has been undertaken in order to assess its nutritive value. The present communication is concerned with a chemical study of the main protein in the grain.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The grain used in this investigation was obtained from the Koilpatti Agricultural Station (Madras). It was sun-dried and ground to a fine meal (40-mesh) which had the following composition: moisture, 7.92% ; ash, 2.34% ; ether extractives, 6.8% ; crude protein, 9.27% ; crude fibre, 2.3% ; carbohydrates (by difference), 71.87%. The ratio of husk to grain was about 8.

As will be seen the meal contains nearly 10% of protein and a rather characteristically large proportion of ether extractives. The finely ground meal was dried in large desiccators under vacuum and preserved in glass stoppered bottles.

Distribution of Nitrogen in the Meal.—To ascertain the distribution of nitrogen in the meal it was extracted successively with different solvents and the nitrogen extracted determined by Kjeldahl's method in the clear extracts. The results were as follows: water, 13.04% ; 6% sodium chloride, 8.69% ; 70% cold ethyl alcohol, 83.27% ; 70% hot ethyl alcohol, 6.95% ; 0.04% sodium hydroxide, 9.06%. 71% of the nitrogen in the meal has been accounted for

and it may be possible by repeated extraction with the above named solvents to account for nearly 90-95% of the nitrogen in the meal. It should be noted that more than 50% of the extractable nitrogen comes in the alcoholic extract, suggesting that most of the protein is the one usually known as 'prolamin.' As this forms the major portion of the protein in the cereal it formed the first object of the study.

Optimum Conditions of Extraction of the 'Prolamin.'

Mode of Extraction.—The first point to be investigated was the mode of extraction. Equal quantities of the meal were treated as follows (duration of extraction same): (a) stirring and filtering, (b) shaking and filtering, and (c) shaking and centrifuging. Aliquots of the extracts gave the following percentages for nitrogen extracted: (a) 32.4, (b) 32.4 and (c) 26.7. So in the subsequent experiments (b) was the mode of extraction adopted.

Influence of Concentration of Alcohol.—The next point to be investigated was the influence of concentration of the alcohol used. To 5 g. of the vacuum-dried meal were added 50 c.c. of ethyl alcohol of varying concentration and shaken for two hours at room temperature (25°). After filtration nitrogen in the extract was determined. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Concentration (by vol.)	Nitrogen extracted.	Concentration (by vol.)	Nitrogen extracted.	Concentration (by vol.)	Nitrogen extracted.
0%	15.21%	40%	7.02%	70%	31.97%
10	10.24	50	7.14	75	30.42
20	8.69	60	23.9	80	29.54
30	7.64	65	30.9	90	28.43

It is evident from the results that 70% alcohol is most suited for extraction. This may probably be due to the fact that the protein in the seed can be separated into two fractions: one water-soluble—the so-called 'globulin,' and the other peptisable by a mixture of water and alcohol—the 'prolamine' (see, however, Gortner, *Kolloid Z.*, 1928, 44, 97, on the inadequateness of the present classification). One has also to take into account the influence of such various factors as viscosity, surface tension, solvation, dipolemoment, association, etc., when dealing with peptisation by mixed solvents. Ostwald (*Kolloid Z.*, 1928, 45, 58, 381) has drawn attention to the great rôle

played by dipolemoment in such phenomena, and Jirgensons (*Kolloid Z.*, 1929, 47, 236) has published some interesting experiments on the coagulation of strongly solvated sols with organic substances and water. He found that alcohols *sensitised* in presence of salts when the concentration of the alcohol was low but they acted as stabilisers in higher concentrations. A similar behaviour is noticeable here. Ethyl alcohol acts as a sensitiser up to a concentration of 60% and thereafter acts as a stabiliser. The meal used for the extraction of the protein contains 2.3% of ash and hence it is quite conceivable that the process is akin to that observed by Jirgensons. However we shall report in a subsequent paper a detailed experimental investigation of this question.

Influence of Period of Extraction.—Having studied the influence of concentration of the alcohol, the effect of period of extraction was examined. The results are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Period of extraction.	Nitrogen extracted.	Period of extraction.	Nitrogen extracted.
1 hr.	31.28%	4 hrs.	32.15%
3 hrs.	33.09	5½ hrs.	32.15
3½ hrs.	32.15		

Three hours gave the best results and was finally adopted for the preparation of the protein. The lower amount of nitrogen extracted for longer periods may probably be due to denaturation of the protein.

Influence of the Quantity of Meal taken.—Much stress has been laid by Ostwald and collaborators (*Kolloid Z.*, 1927, 41, 163; 43 249) on the rôle of the quantity of the solid phase in 'colloid solubility'. So the influence of the quantity of the meal taken on the nitrogen extracted was tried. The results are given in Table III.

TABLE III.

Quantity of meal taken (g.).	5	12.5	15	30	22.5
Nitrogen extracted (g.).	0.21515	0.47532	0.5847	0.7372	0.80635
Nitrogen extracted (percentage).					
1st extraction	34.33	34.57	32.46	30.66	29.67
2nd extraction	5.66	3.30	4.49	4.46	4.64
3rd extraction	3.04	1.74	2.03	1.74	1.55
Total	43.03	39.61	38.98	36.86	35.86

The results indicate that the quantity of nitrogen extracted increases with the quantity of the solid phase. If the percentage of nitrogen extracted is taken into account for a single extraction the maximum is attained when the ratio of meal to solvent is 1:4. If the sum of three consecutive extractions is considered then the maximum percentage is attained with the least quantity of the solid phase.

Preparation of Typhoidin.

Several batches of 200 g. of the meal were extracted with 800 c.c. of 70% alcohol at room temperature in glass stoppered bottles for three hours. The extract was filtered under suction and the filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure at 40-45° keeping the concentration of alcohol constant by addition of alcohol now and again, thus preventing the precipitation of the protein during concentration. The concentrated extract was poured into 20 litres of distilled water contained in tall glass cylinders under constant stirring when a milky suspension was obtained. To this a saturated solution of pure sodium chloride was added and the contents let stand for two days. During this period the protein had settled to the bottom of the cylinder. The supernatant liquid was syphoned off and the turbid bottom liquid centrifuged. The protein was washed on the centrifuge several times with distilled water to remove sodium chloride. It was then dissolved in hot 75% alcohol and reprecipitated. This process was again repeated. The protein so prepared was pressed between filter papers and dried in a vacuum desiccator. The powdered material was extracted with ether to remove ether-soluble impurities, dried *in vacuo* and powdered. The yield of pure product was about 30 g. per kg. of meal taken. The purity of the preparation was tested by estimation of nitrogen in different preparations which was found to be identical. The protein thus prepared was a light grey powder mostly soluble in 75% alcohol. It contains sulphur but no phosphorus.

Elementary Composition of Typhoidin.—Elementary analysis of the protein gave the following results (Table IV).

TABLE IV.

Element.	Percentage.		Average.
	I	II	
Carbon	56.4	57.18	56.79
Hydrogen	5.48	5.65	5.565
Nitrogen	15.3	15.3	15.3
Sulphur	0.61	0.60	0.605
Oxygen (by diffe).	22.21	21.27	21.74

Nitrogen was estimated according to Kjeldahl, carbon and hydrogen by combustion and sulphur according to Trotman and Bell (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1926, 45, 12).

Nitrogen Distribution in Typhoidin.—About three g. of the protein were hydrolysed by boiling under reflux with five parts of 25% hydrochloric acid till the liquid no longer gave any biuret reaction. It was found that 80 hours were sufficient. The hydrolysate was evaporated in *vacuo* to a sticky mass to remove hydrochloric acid. To the residue ammonia-free water was added and again concentrated in *vacuo*. The dry residue was now taken up with water and made up to 200 c.c. The nitrogen in the insoluble residue was determined according to Kjeldahl and was taken to represent acid-insoluble humin.

The filtrate was used for the estimation of nitrogen distribution according to Van Slyke, due regard being paid to all the improvements suggested by Plimmer and Rosedale (*Biochem. J.*, 1925, 19, 104; Daft, *Biochem. J.*, 1929, 23, 149). Arginine was estimated in the hydrolysate after removal of amide nitrogen as also the acid soluble melanin nitrogen according to Plimmer (*Biochem. J.*, 1916, 10, 115), adopting however the apparatus of Linderström-Lang (*Compt. rend. Carlsberg*, 1927-29, 17, No. 9, 25). Plimmer has drawn attention to the fact that the arginine is not completely precipitated by phosphotungstic acid and the discrepancy noticed between the direct estimation in the hydrolysate and that in the basic fraction was easily accounted for by the arginine nitrogen in the mono-amino-fraction. The results are given in Table V.

TABLE V.

Nitrogen distribution in typhoidin (percentages of total nitrogen).

Form of nitrogen.	Percentage.	
Amide	21.31	
Humins :	2.59	
Insoluble		1.68
Soluble		0.96
Basic :	10.23	
Arginine		4.55
Histidine		2.49
Cystine		1.80
Lysine		1.39
Non-Basic :	64.66	
Amino		63.51
Non-amino		1.15
Total	98.79	

TABLE Va.

Nitrogen distribution of typhoidin as compared with that of other prolamins.

Form of nitrogen.	Typhoidin from <i>Pennisetum typhoides</i> .	Gliadin from <i>Triticum vulgare</i> .	Eleusine from <i>Eleusine corocana</i> .	Sorghumin from <i>Sorghum vulgare</i> .	Zein from <i>Zea mays</i> .
Amide	21.31	25.52	20.52	18.96	16.06
Humins	2.59	0.87	1.17	3.08	1.11
Basic :					
Arginine	4.55	6.38	2.60	4.63	3.92
Histidine	2.49	5.41	2.69	1.19	2.45
Cystine	1.80	1.68	—	0.92	0.98
Lysine	1.39	0.57	0.64	3.45	0.89
Non-basic :					
Amino	63.51	53.49	69.03	60.01	66.08
Non-amino	1.15	6.14	2.13	5.33	5.90
Total	98.79				

Essential Amino-acids.—In order to correctly judge the nutritive value of the protein, accurate analysis of the essential amino-acids should be made. Cystine figures obtained by Van Slyke's method are incorrect—being racemised during hydrolysis it is incompletely precipitated by phosphotungstic acid. It was therefore estimated according to the methods of Sullivan (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1927, 74, 14) and of Folin and Looney (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1922, 51, 421). Tryptophan was estimated colourimetrically according to Folin and Looney (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1922, 51, 421). Tyrosine was estimated according to Zuwerkalow (*Z. Physiol. Chem.*, 1926, 163, 185) as also according to Folin and Looney (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1922, 51, 421). The results are given in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Percentages of the essential amino-acids in typhoidin and other prolamins determined by different methods.

Amino-acid.	Typhoidin.	Eleusinina.	Gliadin.	Zein.	Method.
Arginine	2.19	2.23			Van Slyke
Histidine	1.42	1.13			"
Lysine	1.12	0.46			"
Cystine	1.81	1.39	2.32	0.50	Folin and Looney
"	1.52				Sullivan
Tyrosine	2.82	2.03			Zuwerkalow
"	2.49				Folin and Looney
Tryptophane	2.77		3.4	5.52	Folin and Looney
"		1.59			Koom.
"			1.14	0	

It is clear from the tables that typhoidin is not lacking in essential amino-acids. It compares favourably with other cereals in regard to the basic nitrogen it contains. It is similar to sorghumin but essentially superior to eleusinina. Its cystine content is higher than that of the other prolamins. The cystine content of typhoidin does not account for all the sulphur in the protein. This suggests that probably another sulphur containing amino-acid is present.

This point is receiving our attention. It is rich in tryptophane and it is therefore evident that it should be of high nutritive value if supplemented by a protein like cajanin which is deficient in this essential amino-acid but contains useful amounts of the diamino-acids.

Summary.

The chief protein in *Pennisetum typhoideum* is a prolamn which accounts for 43% of the total nitrogen.

The optimum conditions of extraction of the protein have been studied and the possible mechanism of protein peptisation by mixed solvents discussed.

The nitrogen distribution in the protein has been studied and the essential amino-acids determined.

It is characterised by a high content of cystine and tryptophane. The sulphur content suggest the presence of another sulphur-containing amino-acid.

The nutritive value of the protein has been discussed.

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